

Report created during voluntary work at the University of Manchester (Engineering Division) for prof. Domenico Lombardi

Summary of numerical test results: cyclic triaxial
tests (under constant volume conditions) using 3D
DEM

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0.1 Methodology and Approach

0.1.1 Numerical method

The *PFC^{3D}* code developed by ITASCA was used to perform all simulations mentioned in this report ([?]). The code follows closely the discrete element method introduced by [?]. The model is composed of distinct particles that displace independently of one another, and interact only at the contact or interfaces between particles. The particles are assumed rigid with no ability to rotate to roughly mimic the increased strength due to non-spherical particle shapes ([?]). To achieve rapid convergence the simulations also employ a small amount of nonviscous local damping, δ . The contact law employed is linear elasto-plastic. The normal and tangential stiffness at any contact, k_n and k_s , are described by the following scaling rule:

$$\begin{aligned} k_n &= 2 * K_{ceff} * \frac{D_1 D_2}{D_1 + D_2} \\ k_s &= \alpha k_n \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where K_{ceff} , α are parameters to be calibrated; D_1 , D_2 are the contacting spheres. The plastic part of the contact law is given by the interparticle friction angle, ϕ_μ . No cohesion was included in the contact model. Macroscopic stiffness is insensitive to particle scaling factor ([?]) when normal and tangential contact stiffness are described as above (1).

In the first instance the micro parameters (ϕ_μ , K_{ceff} , α and δ) were selected as calibrated in [?]. The authors performed numerical simulations of drained triaxial test on discrete material analogue of Toyoura sand. The best fitting was obtained for the parameters listed in Table 1.

Parameter	Unit	Symbol	Value1	Value2
Particle friction coefficient	[-]	$\tan(\phi_\mu)$	0.33	0.65
Coefficient K_{ceff}	[MPa]	K_{ceff}	60	20
Local damping	[-]	δ	0.05	0.05
Particle density	[kg/m ³]	ρ_g	2650	2650
Stiffness ratio	[-]	α	0.25	0.25

Table 1: DEM model parameters

0.1.2 Sample preparation

The numerical sample was cylindrical with diameter of 4 mm and height of 8 mm (Figure 1a). The cylindrical region was filled with 19700 spherical particles with the grain size distribution shown in Figure 1b. Specimen was created to a porosity slightly above the target value using the Radius

Expansion Method (REM). In this method all particles are created with a radius smaller than their target, and then all radii are incrementally expanded until porosity is close to the objective. Target porosity was 0.48. The sample was also built with wall elements that can be either fixed or servo-controlled to maintain a specified boundary stress and/or strain. The walls were frictionless. After sample generation the velocities were then reset to zero. Isotropic compression to 10 kPa in which the interparticle friction might be reduced was used to obtain—by trial and error—a closer fit to the relative density target. Interparticle friction was then reset to the calibrated value and isotropic stress ramped up to the target value. The sample was compressed by controlled movement of all walls (top, bottom and outer). After that the cyclic undrained triaxial test was simulated. The volume of the sample was maintained constant during test. The 'constant volume procedure' was implemented in the code.

Figure 1: (a) DEM assembly of spheres (b) particle size distribution curves

0.1.3 Testing program

The model aims to reproduce selected experimental cyclic triaxial tests on Toyoura Sand performed by Domenico Lombardi (reference) and listed in Table 2.

Test ID	D_R	p	e	Test Type	Δq	Comment
TY-1	38	50	0.845	TXC	20	Impossible to create such a loose sample with the parameters (Value1) from Table 1 and/or REM generation procedure
TY-2	50	50	0.805	TXC	15	Relative density slightly different than the experimental
TY-2a	67	100	0.749	TXC	40	-
TY-3	82	100	0.699	TXC	60	-
CU - cyclic undrained triaxial $e_{max} = 0.97$ $e_{min} = 0.64$						

Table 2: Summary of experimental tests

**0.1.4 Macro-results for Calibration Parameters: Value1
Ty-2-NUM**

Sand	D_R [%]	e [-]	p [kPa]	Δq [kPa]	frequency [Hz]
Toyoura Sand	52.4	0.797	50	15	100

Table 3: TEST TY-2-NUM

Figure 2: Cyclic loading:TY-2-NUM

Figure 3: Stress strain behaviour: TY-2-NUM

Figure 4: Stress path: TY-2-NUM

Figure 5: Development of axial strain: TY-2-NUM

Figure 6: Development of stresses: TY-2-NUM

Figure 7: Accumulation of pore water pressure: TY-2-NUM

Ty-2a-NUM

Sand	D_R [%]	e [-]	p [kPa]	Δq [kPa]	frequency [Hz]
Toyoura Sand	67	0.749	100	40	100

Table 4: TEST TY-2a-NUM

Figure 8: Cyclic loading:TY-2a-NUM

Figure 9: Stress strain behaviour: TY-2a-NUM

Figure 10: Stress path: TY-2a-NUM

Figure 11: Development of axial strain: TY-2a-NUM

Figure 12: Development of stresses: TY-2a-NUM

Figure 13: Accumulation of pore water pressure: TY-2a-NUM

Ty-3-NUM

Sand	D_R [%]	e [-]	p [kPa]	Δq [kPa]	frequency [Hz]
Toyoura Sand	82	0.700	100	60	100

Table 5: TEST TY-3-NUM

Figure 14: Cyclic loading:TY-3-NUM

Figure 15: Stress strain behaviour: TY-3-NUM

Figure 16: Stress path: TY-3-NUM

Figure 17: Development of axial strain: TY-3-NUM

Figure 18: Development of stresses: TY-3-NUM

Figure 19: Accumulation of pore water pressure: TY-3-NUM

0.1.5 Macro-results for Calibration Parameters: Value2
Ty-1-NUM-v2

Sand	D_R [%]	e [-]	p [kPa]	Δq [kPa]	frequency [Hz]
Toyoura Sand	43.9	0.826	50	20	100

Table 6: TEST TY-1-NUM-v2

Figure 20: Cyclic loading:TY-1-NUM-v2

Figure 21: Stress strain behaviour: TY-1-NUM-v2

Figure 22: Stress path: TY-1-NUM-v2

Figure 23: Development of axial strain: TY-1-NUM-v2

Figure 24: Development of stresses: TY-1-NUM-v2

Figure 25: Accumulation of pore water pressure: TY-1-NUM-v2

Ty-2-NUM-v2

Sand	D_R [%]	e [-]	p [kPa]	Δq [kPa]	frequency [Hz]
Toyoura Sand	49.4	0.807	50	15	100

Table 7: TEST TY-2-NUM-v2

Figure 26: Cyclic loading:TY-2-NUM-v2

Figure 27: Stress strain behaviour: TY-2-NUM-v2

Figure 28: Stress path: TY-2-NUM-v2

Figure 29: Development of axial strain: TY-2-NUM-v2

Figure 30: Development of stresses: TY-2-NUM-v2

Figure 31: Accumulation of pore water pressure: TY-2-NUM-v2

Ty-3-NUM-v2

Sand	D_R [%]	e [-]	p [kPa]	Δq [kPa]	frequency [Hz]
Toyoura Sand	82	0.700	100	60	2000

Table 8: TEST TY-3-NUM-v2

Figure 32: Cyclic loading:TY-3-NUM-v2

Figure 33: Stress strain behaviour: TY-3-NUM-v2

Figure 34: Stress path: TY-3-NUM-v2

Figure 35: Development of axial strain: TY-3-NUM-v2

Figure 36: Development of stresses: TY-3-NUM-v2

Figure 37: Accumulation of pore water pressure: TY-3-NUM-v2

0.1.6 Initial conditions: homogeneity

The homogeneity of the specimen was initially assessed by observation of the average contact normal orientations (Figure 38) and contact normal force orientations (Figure 39).

Figure 38: Orientation of contacts

Figure 39: Orientation and magnitude of contact forces

0.1.7 Distribution of Contact Forces-TY-2-NUM

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 40: (a) cyclic loading; (b) Stress path; (c) stress strain behaviour

Figure 41: Distribution of contact forces (black: contact forces greater than average value; grey: contact forces smaller than average value)

Figure 42: Orientation of contacts during cyclic loading

0.1.8 Distribution of Contact Forces-TY-2a-NUM

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 43: (a) cyclic loading; (b) Stress path; (c) stress strain behaviour

Figure 44: Distribution of contact forces (black: contact forces greater than average value; grey: contact forces smaller than average value)

Figure 45: Orientation of contacts during cyclic loading

Bibliography